

Preparation for the Gospel-Demonstration of the Gospel

also known as “Praeparatio evangelica”, “Demonstratio Evangelica”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Christian Theology, Early Christian Text, Apologetics, Early Christianity, Orthodoxy

The “Praeparatio Evangelica” and the “Demonstratio Evangelica” of Eusebius of Caesarea are two parts of a single treatise that was apparently the most comprehensive apologetic and polemical work written in the early Christian era. The text attempts to prove the excellence of Christianity over every pagan religion and philosophy, on the one hand. On the other, it focuses on Christianity's relationship to Judaism as the fulfillment of biblical prophecies. The “Praeparatio Evangelica” consists of fifteen books which have been completely preserved, while the “Demonstratio Evangelica” comprised twenty, of which only the first ten have survived. Both works are addressed to the same audience, that is, new Christians of Gentile origin, and curious, educated pagans willing to learn about Christianity. Christian apologists had to fight against the claim that Christianity was a danger to the state, a crime against the official cult and religion and even against the Emperor himself. They fought for their legal and moral right to exist. Emphasizing the superiority of Christian morality and decency over the corrupt and degenerate social mores of the pagans, Christian apologists leveled against them the very same accusations which the pagans had used against Christianity. The apologists sought to weaken anti-Christian bias and to underline the superiority of Christianity over other religions and cults. Their attempt explains the often repeated claim that the Christian faith played a major role in maintaining world order, the status of the Emperor and the integrity of state and society. According to the apologists, a rational defense of the faith was necessary for the establishment of the right of the Christians to exist. Along with their effort to expose the absurdity and corruption of pagan religion, mythology and social norms, the apologists offered proof that only Christianity possessed a true understanding of God and of the universe. In this sense, the “Praeparatio Evangelica” is a quite interesting work, not so much because of its polemical content, but because of the abundance of its citations from the now lost works of ancient authors. Eusebius studied the “Praeparatio Evangelica” with many fragments from historians and philosophers, which are nowhere else preserved. The “Praeparatio Evangelica” preserves Pyrrho's translation of the Buddhist three marks of existence, upon which Pyrrho based Pyrrhonism; the text also provides a summary of the writings of the Phoenician priest Sanchuniathon, of which the accuracy has been shown by the mythological accounts found on the Ugaritic tables; the account of Diodorus Siculus on the wondrous voyage of Euhemerus to the island of Panchaea, where Euhemerus purports to have found the true history of the gods; it preserves fragments from the writings of the neoplatonic philosopher Atticus. There are no quotes from comedy, tragedy, or lyric poetry, but there are references to all the works of Plato and to an extensive range of later philosophic works, largely from Middle Platonists from Philo to the late 2nd century, as well as several more fragments from now lost works. The author of the text, Eusebius of Caesarea, c. 260/265–339, also known as Eusebius Pamphilus, was historian of Christianity, exegete, and Christian polemicist. He became the bishop of Caesarea Maritima, where he was born, in the Roman province of Syria Palaestina in around 314. He composed the texts in question between 313 and 324 CE, as apologetic works for the practice of verbal confrontation with Greeks and Jews. He conceived his apologetic work with a threefold purpose: To shatter the foundations of pagan religion and philosophy; To demonstrate that the Hebrew religion and philosophy are superior in every way to pagan culture; And to explain how Christianity diverges from Judaism and is thereby superior. The first part of the text, the “Praeparatio Evangelica” attempts to prove the superiority of Christianity by criticizing pagan religion and philosophy. The second part, the

“Demonstratio Evangelica”, was intended to prove the validity of Christianity and the Gospel as the fulfillment of ancient prophecies. This could happen only after the reader of pagan origin had received suitable “preparation”, that is, the preparation for the presentation-demonstration of the Gospel. Hence, the “Praeparatio Evangelica” treats subjects familiar to the educated pagan, such as religion, mythology, philosophy, cosmology, theology, and ethics. At the “Demonstratio Evangelica” Eusebius proceeds to deal with particular problems that Christian belief presented to the educated pagan, such as the Son of God or the Logos, the incarnation, virgin birth, passion, crucifixion and resurrection.

Date Range: 312 CE - 324 CE

Region: Caesarea Maritima

Region tags: Middle East, Eastern Mediterranean, Israel

Caesarea Maritima, Eusebius's of Caesarea place of birth.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: E. H. Gifford, "Preparation for the Gospel", 2 Vols (Grand Rapids: Baker Book House, 1981).
- Source 2: W. J. Ferrar, (ed. and trans.), "The Proof of the Gospel" (Grand Rapids: Baker Book House, 1981).
- Source 3: I. A. Heikel, "Eusebius Werke VI. Die Demonstratio Evangelica" (Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, 1913).

Notes: -K. Mras, "Eusebius Werke VIII. Die Praeparatio Evangelica" (Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, 1954, 1956). - Eusèbe de Césarée, "La Préparation évangélique". Livre I, Introduction, texte grec, traduction et commentaire par Jean Sirinelli et Édouard des Places, s.j., Sources Chrétiennes 206, Paris 1974.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://en-academic.com/dic.nsf/enwiki/11623792>
- Source 1 Description: Praeparatio Evangelica
- Source 2 URL: <https://chs.harvard.edu/chapter/part-ii-didacticismaaron-p-johnson-eusebius-praeparatio-evangelica-as-literary-experiment/>
- Source 2 Description: Eusebius' Praeparatio Evangelica as Literary Experiment
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.vision.org/biography-eusebius-pamphilus-father-church-history-434>
- Source 3 Description: Eusebius Pamphilus

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/eusebius_pe_00_intro.htm

- Source 1 Description: Eusebius of Caesarea: Praeparatio Evangelica
 - Source 2 URL: <http://remacle.org/bloodwolf/historiens/eusebe/index.htm#PRE>
 - Source 2 Description: PRÉPARATION ÉVANGÉLIQUE
 - Source 3 URL: https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/eusebius_de_03_book1.htm
 - Source 3 Description: Eusebius of Caesarea: Demonstratio Evangelica
- Notes: -Evangelicae praeparationis libri XV ad codices manuscriptos
<https://archive.org/details/evangelicaepraep01euse/page/n53/mode/2up>

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

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Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

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– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The author, however, wrote two works about the Emperor Constantine (272 CE-337 CE), the "Life of Constantine" and a sermon "In Praise of Constantine". Eusebius did not hide his intention of relating only those details that concerned the Emperor's religious character and Christian devotion. Eusebius wished that both of his works about Emperor Constantine would be educational, and the figure of Constantine a model for imitation, since the source of the Emperor's greatness was his absolute faith in God and his constant devotion to Him. Eusebius presented Constantine as an example for future rulers, a devoutly Christian Emperor acting as a messenger of the Christian God. Through the biography, hence, of the Emperor Eusebius aimed to defend and preach the benefits of Christianity.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, the text aims to convince its readers to embrace Christian faith. According to the author himself, the main goal of both "Praeparatio Evangelica" and "Demonstratio Evangelica" was to present and prove the doctrine of the Gospel and the dogmas of the Christian faith. With the encyclopedic character of his work Eusebius attempts to interpret the traditional world, that is the pagan world, with its religion, mythology, history and philosophy, in a new and different light. The text, hence, has two major interrelated aspects: an educational and didactic, and a polemical one.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The author, however, wrote two works about the Emperor Constantine (272 CE-337 CE), the "Life of Constantine" and a sermon "In Praise of Constantine". Eusebius did not hide his intention of relating only those details that concerned the Emperor's religious character and Christian devotion. Eusebius wished that both of his works about Emperor Constantine would be educational, and the figure of Constantine a model for imitation, since the source of the Emperor's greatness was his absolute faith in God and his constant devotion to Him. Eusebius presented Constantine as an example for future rulers,

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Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

- Field doesn't know
- No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Bibliography

Notes: A sort of bibliography. The text, in fact, contains an abundance of citations from now lost works of several ancient authors. There are many fragments from historians and philosophers, which are nowhere else preserved.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

- No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

- Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

- Yes

Notes: The text refers to the constant habit of the Jewish people to pick out the prophecies which are more favorable to themselves, and to have them ever on their lips. The author arrays against them his proofs from the prophecies about the Gentiles, making it clear how full they are of predictions of good and salvation for all nations, and how strongly they asserted that their promises to the Gentile world could only be fulfilled by the coming of the Christ.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

- No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

- Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

- Field doesn't know

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

- Field doesn't know

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: According to the prophecies cited by the text, all the nations should be blessed by the Messiah

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– I don't know

– I don't know

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: However, the text refers to castrations of mythological beings.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The "Praeparatio Evangelica" and the "Demonstratio Evangelica" are two parts of a single treatise that was the most comprehensive apologetic and polemical work written in the early Christian era. The "Praeparatio Evangelica" consists of fifteen books which have been completely preserved, while the "Demonstratio Evangelica" comprised twenty, of which only the first ten have survived. Both works are addressed to the same audience, that is, new Christians of Gentile origin, and curious, educated pagans willing to learn about Christianity.

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– I don't know

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: However, the text cites extensively Porphyry's "On Abstinence from Animal foods", a work that presents a range of arguments against meat-eating, offering a broad view of the ancient debate concerning animals and their treatment. Abstinence is often taken to be concerned primarily with the health of the human soul. By approaching Abstinence as a work of moral suasion subordinated to a self-directed principle of purity. This call to vegetarianism points to a life characterized by radical self-control,

free of the bad mixture, impurity, and harmfulness that meat-eating entails. Furthermore, there are references in the text as regards to Jewish fasting customs.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Eusebius' work is part of the Christian apologetic literature and it has bern seen as the culmination of the apologetic tradition.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Apologetic literature

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: However the text provides information regarding some taboos found in various religions, such as the Brahmins who do not taste animal food and the Jews, who distinguish the kinds of food, from which one must abstain, and which one must adopt.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

|

↳ Personal effects?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable/precious items?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods?
– Yes
Notes: burnt-offerings, drink-offerings and libations, incense-offerings

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes some references to some Jewish burial rituals, explaining that they do not perform costly funeral rites, neither they erect conspicuous monuments, but appointing the nearest relations to perform the usual obsequies, and made it customary for all who were passing by at the time of a burial to draw near and join in the mourning. The text also refers to the commandment that the house and its inhabitants be purified from the defilement of death, in order that one who has committed murder may be very far from thinking that he is undefiled. Furthermore, there are several in passing references to Egyptian burial customs.

↳ As cenotaphs?
– No

↳ In cemetery?
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?
– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?
– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type?
– Yes

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: However, the text mentions human sacrifice to Kronos on the sixth day of the month Metageitnion. This custom prevailed for a long time before it was changed: for one of those who had been publicly condemned to death was kept in custody until the festival of Kronos, and when the festival was come, they brought the man forth outside the gates opposite the temple of Aristobule, gave him a drink of wine, and cut his throat.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes a reference to the father of Epigeius and Ge (earth) whose father was deified after his death, so they offered him libations and sacrifices.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The text depict these beings as evil and hostile to humanity.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes several references to the pantheon of the Greek Gods, as well as to the gods of other religions, such as the Egyptian, the Phoenician etc.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Field doesn't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Other beings are mentioned in the text, such as Centaurs, Titans or other mythological entities.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, the texts pour scorn on divination practices of the pagans -more particular of philosophers. According to the text, their divination is not from any divine power in them, but from observation of the stars according to mathematical principles. Such practice is not the work of a higher or more divine nature. Furthermore, such practices destroy man's free-will, by referring not only external events and things independent of us, but also our own purposes, to the course of the stars.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that the text refers to sacrifices and offerings in a polemical context, with the view to prove that they are useless. After all, one of the major anti-Christian accusation was that the Christians had greatly erred in not honoring the divine powers and their cults. The important issue of sacrifices had been discussed in the text in the framework of the critique of pagan religion in its various forms. In this discussion, the author of the text exploits the various opinions raised by various pagan authors in order to point out contradictions, to point out the futility of offering sacrifices and the inferior religious position that such a practice denoted. The true sacrifice was service of the heart and silent prayer. In order to rebut pagans, the author of the text mentions opinions of pagan authors who viewed the development of sacrifice in the history of religion as a symptom of the degeneration of mankind. These authors pointed out the negative educational effect of offering sacrifices: when a child learned that the gods enjoyed expensive feasts of animal flesh, he would never prefer moderation and thrift. If he believed that the gods desired such sacrifices, he would inevitably think that he could do evil, in the certain knowledge that he could atone for his sin through such a sacrifice.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to sacrifices of bulls, oxen, sheep, birds etc.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings?
(I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?

–Specify: libations, incense

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The “Praeparatio Evangelica” and the “Demonstratio Evangelica” are two parts of a single treatise that was the most comprehensive apologetic and polemical work written in the early Christian era. The “Praeparatio Evangelica” consists of fifteen books which have been completely preserved, while the “Demonstratio Evangelica” comprised twenty, of which only the first ten have survived. Both works are addressed to the same audience, that is, new Christians of Gentile origin, and curious, educated pagans willing to learn about Christianity.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Eusebius' work is part of the Christian apologetic literature and it has been seen as the culmination of the apologetic tradition.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Apologetic literature

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Bibliography

Notes: A sort of bibliography. The text, in fact, contains an abundance of citations from now lost works of several ancient authors. There are many fragments from historians and philosophers, which are nowhere else preserved.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

↳ Personal effects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: burnt-offerings, drink-offerings and libations, incense-offerings

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes some references to some Jewish burial rituals, explaining that they do not perform costly funeral rites, neither they erect conspicuous monuments, but appointing the nearest relations to perform the usual obsequies, and made it customary for all who were passing by at the time of a burial to draw near and join in the mourning. The text also refers to the commandment that the house and its inhabitants be purified from the defilement of death, in order that one who has committed murder may be very far from thinking that he is undefiled. Furthermore, there are several in passing references to Egyptian burial customs.

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes a reference to the father of Epigeius and Ge (earth) whose father was deified after his death, so they offered him libations and sacrifices.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: The text depict these beings as evil and hostile to humanity.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes several references to the pantheon of the Greek Gods, as well as to the gods of other religions, such as the Egyptian, the Phoenician etc.

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
 - No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?
 - Yes
- ↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?
 - Field doesn't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Other beings are mentioned in the text, such as Centaurs, Titans or other mythological entities.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: On the contrary, the texts pour scorn on divination practices of the pagans -more particular of philosophers. According to the text, their divination is not from any divine power in them, but from observation of the stars according to mathematical principles. Such practice is not the work of a higher or more divine nature. Furthermore, such practices destroy man's free-will, by referring not only external events and things independent of us, but also our own purposes, to the course of the stars.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– I don't know

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– I don't know

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to the constant habit of the Jewish people to pick out the prophecies which are more favorable to themselves, and to have them ever on their lips. The author arrays against them his proofs from the prophecies about the Gentiles, making it clear how full they are of predictions of good and salvation for all nations, and how strongly they asserted that their promises to the Gentile world could only be fulfilled by the coming of the Christ.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Field doesn't know

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: According to the prophecies cited by the text, all the nations should be blessed by the Messiah

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: However, the text refers to castrations of mythological beings.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: However, the text cites extensively Porphyry's "On Abstinence from Animal foods", a work that presents a range of arguments against meat-eating, offering a broad view of the ancient debate concerning animals and their treatment. Abstinence is often taken to be concerned primarily with the health of the human soul. By approaching Abstinence as a work of moral suasion subordinated to a self-directed principle of purity. This call to vegetarianism points to a life characterized by radical self-control, free of the bad mixture, impurity, and harmfulness that meat-eating entails. Furthermore, there are references in the text as regards to Jewish fasting customs.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: However the text provides information regarding some taboos found in various religions, such as the Brahmans who do not taste animal food and the Jews, who distinguish the kinds of food, from which one must abstain, and which one must adopt.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: However, the text mentions human sacrifice to Kronos on the sixth day of the month Metageitnion. This custom prevailed for a long time before it was changed: for one of those who had been publicly condemned to death was kept in custody until the festival of Kronos, and when the festival was come, they brought the man forth outside the gates opposite the temple of Aristobule, gave him a drink of wine, and cut his throat.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that the text refers to sacrifices and offerings in a polemical context, with the view to prove that they are useless. After all, one of the major anti-Christian accusation was that the Christians had greatly erred in not honoring the divine powers and their cults. The important issue of sacrifices had been discussed in the text in the framework of the critique of pagan religion in its various forms. In this discussion, the author of the text exploits the various opinions raised by various pagan

authors in order to point out contradictions, to point out the futility of offering sacrifices and the inferior religious position that such a practice denoted. The true sacrifice was service of the heart and silent prayer. In order to rebut pagans, the author of the text mentions opinions of pagan authors who viewed the development of sacrifice in the history of religion as a symptom of the degeneration of mankind. These authors pointed out the negative educational effect of offering sacrifices: when a child learned that the gods enjoyed expensive feasts of animal flesh, he would never prefer moderation and thrift. If he believed that the gods desired such sacrifices, he would inevitably think that he could do evil, in the certain knowledge that he could atone for his sin through such a sacrifice.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to sacrifices of bulls, oxen, sheep, birds etc.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?

– Specify: libations, incense

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to various schools of Antiquity, mainly philosophical, such as the Platonic (Academy), the Peripatetic, the School of Xenophanes and Parmenides, the School of Aristippus, the school of Anaxagoras in Lampsacus, the School of Metrodorus and Protagoras, the School of Epicurus, the School of Crates, the School of Pyrrho, the Eleatic school and the school of Pythagoras, the School of Mnesarchus the Stoic etc. Furthermore, references to the schools of sophistry at Delphi and Dodona.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

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– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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